

Synthesis and Characterisation of some New Aminoacidato Complexes of Nickel(II)

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The coordination behaviour of l-leucine and *N*-benzoylglycine has been reported by isolating and characterising some aminoacidato complexes of nickel(II) having the general formula $Ni(AA)_2$, $Ni(AA)_2 \cdot xL$ and $Ni(AA)(OOCR)$, where AA = l-leucine and *N*-benzoylglycine anions; L = n-hexylamine, piperidine, pyridine, 2,2'-bipyridine, ethanol, isopropanol, t-butanol and tetrahydrofuran; R = C_2H_5 , C_3H_7 and C_4H_9 ; and x = 1 or 2. Spectral and magnetic data indicate octahedral environment around nickel(II). Ligand field parameters have been calculated and discussed. The IR data reveal the bidentate nature of aminoacid anions in these complexes.

BIOCHEMICAL importance of several aminoacids and their complexes with transition metals is well documented¹. A survey of the literature revealed comparatively extensive studies^{2,3} on Cr^{III} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with aminoacids, and very little for Ni^{II} complexes^{4,5}. While most of the work carried out on the nickel(II)-aminoacid complexes in solution^{6,7}, a very limited attention seems to have been paid on the isolation and characterisation of solid complexes^{8,9}. As a part of our programme¹⁰ of investigation of the coordination behaviour of l-leucine and *N*-benzoylglycine, the present communication reports the isolation and physicochemical characterisation of some bis-complexes of nickel(II) with these amino acids. Also, a few mixed ligand complexes of nickel(II) with straight chain carboxylic acid and amino acid having general formula $Ni(AA)(OOCR)$, have been synthesised by exploiting substitution reaction of nickel(II) acetate. These complexes are also characterised to throw some light on their structural behaviour.

Experimental

Nickel chloride hexahydrate (B.D.H.) was made anhydrous by heating it carefully at about 200° in an atmosphere of dry hydrogen chloride gas. Nickel acetate was made anhydrous by heating $Ni(OOCCH_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ for 4 h under reduced pressure (120°/2 mm). All other reagents were of A.R. grade and rigorously dried.

Molecular weights were determined with a Gallenkamp semimicro-ebullimeter with a thermistor sensing device. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded in the range 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Beckman Acculab-9 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra in the range 4000–28000 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Cary-14 spectrophotometer and ESR spectra

on a Varian E-4 X-band spectrometer operating at 9.5 GHz. Magnetic measurements were carried out with a Gouy balance using ferrous ammonium sulphate as standard and conductivity measurements by a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Nickel was estimated gravimetrically as bisdimethylglyoximate nickel(II) nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method, and alcohol by oxidimetric method¹¹. Acetic acid was titrated with standard sodium hydroxide solution using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Bis(N-benzoylglycinato)nickel(II), $Ni(hip)_2$: A methanolic solution of anhydrous nickel(II) chloride (0.09 mol, 1.16 g) was added to the sodium salt of *N*-benzoylglycine (0.18 mol, 3.23 g, *hipH*, and 0.18 mol, 0.72 g NaOH). The reaction was exothermic and the reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h. Sodium chloride was separated through filtration. The green coloured complex was obtained from bluish green solution after evaporating the excess of the solvent in vacuum (40°/2 mm) and recrystallised from methanol (Found: Ni, 12.3; N, 5.82. $Ni(hip)_2 \cdot 2MeOH$ calcd. for: Ni, 12.26; N, 5.85%). A green solid was obtained after heating the above complex under reduced pressure (135°/2 mm), (88%), m.p., 228° (Found: Ni, 14.02; N, 6.78. $Ni(C_9H_8O_2N)_2$ calcd. for: Ni, 14.14; N, 6.75%).

$Ni(hip)_2 \cdot 2Hex^nNH_2$: $Ni(hip)_2$ (0.06 mol, 2.46 g) was reacted with n-hexylamine (25 ml). The reaction was exothermic and completed by refluxing the mixture for 2 h. The excess of the amine was removed after washing the product several times with n-hexane. The product was finally dried at 48°/2 mm, (85%).

The other addition complexes, $Ni(AA)_2 \cdot xL$, were prepared following the similar procedure as above. The results of elemental analysis are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—AMINOACIDATO COMPLEXES OF Ni²⁺ (Ni(AA)₂ and Ni(AA)₂ · xL)

Sl. no.	Compd *	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)
			Ni	N	Alcohol	
1.	Ni(leu) ₂	Blue	18.25 (18.41)	8.85 (8.78)	—	650 (319)
2.	Ni(hip) ₂	Green	14.02 (14.14)	6.78 (6.75)	—	850 (415)
3.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2EtOH	Sky blue	14.20 (14.28)	6.35 (6.28)	22.90 (22.41)	845 (411)
4.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2Pr ^t OH	Sky blue	13.30 (13.37)	6.35 (6.38)	26.85 (27.37)	890 (439)
5.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2Bu ^t OH	Blue	12.50 (12.57)	6.05 (5.99)	—	—
6.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2THF	Light blue	12.60 (12.68)	6.09 (6.05)	—	945 (463)
7.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2Hex ⁿ NH ₂	Bluish green	11.19 (11.26)	10.70 (10.74)	—	1 058 (521)
8.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2py	Brown	12.21 (12.31)	11.71 (11.74)	—	970 (477)
9.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2pd	Brown	11.85 (12.00)	11.39 (11.45)	—	990 (489)
10.	Ni(leu) ₂ · 2,2'-bipy**	Reddish blue	12.25 (12.36)	11.75 (11.79)	—	960 (475)
11.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2EtOH	Green	11.51 (11.58)	5.60 (5.58)	18.40 (18.17)	1 030 (507)
12.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2Pr ^t OH	Green	10.90 (10.96)	5.20 (5.23)	21.85 (22.46)	1 050 (535)
13.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2Bu ^t OH	Green	10.30 (10.42)	5.00 (4.97)	—	—
14.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2THF	Light green	10.44 (10.50)	5.02 (5.00)	—	—
15.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2Hex ⁿ NH ₂	Brownish green	9.40 (9.50)	9.02 (9.07)	—	1 250 (617)
16.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2py	Greenish brown	10.15 (10.24)	9.80 (9.77)	—	—
17.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2pd	Greenish brown	9.95 (10.02)	9.55 (9.57)	—	1 200 (585)
18.	Ni(hip) ₂ · 2,2'-bipy**	Green	10.20 (10.28)	9.75 (9.80)	—	1 120 (571)

*leu H = l-Leucine, hip H = N-benzoylglycine; all are solid.

**Prepared in methanol.

Ni(leu)(myrist): To anhydrous nickel(II) acetate (0.18 mol, 3.26 g) suspended in toluene, myristic acid (0.18 mol, 4.23 g) was added. The contents were refluxed for 18 h with the removal of the toluene-acetic acid azeotrope continuously from the fractionating column at 106–110°. A clear solution resulted at the end of the reaction. Toluene was removed under reduced pressure (70°/2 mm) to yield the residue Ni(OOCC₁₃H₂₇),

[Found/(calcd.): Ni, 16.93 (17.01%); AcOH in azeotrope, 1.02 (1.10 g). To the above mixed carboxylate (0.07 mol, 1.77 g) dissolved in toluene, l-leucine (0.07 mol, 0.67 g) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed with constant fractionation for 20 h. A green solid was obtained after evaporating the excess solvent under reduced pressure. The product was recrystallised from benzene; its analysis corresponding to Ni(leu)

(myrist). The reactions can be represented as

All the above reactions could be carried out in toluene because of the advantage that it formed azeotrope with the liberated acetic acid at 106°, and removed easily by fractionation during the course of the reactions. The progress of the reactions could be followed by estimating the acetic acid content in the collected azeotrope.

Other mixed ligand complexes, Ni(OOCR)(AA), were also synthesised following the above procedure. The results of elemental analysis are given in Table 2.

Infrared spectra : In the spectra of bis(leucinato)-nickel(II) and bis-(N-benzoylglycinato)nickel(II), the N—H stretching vibrations at 3 460 and 3 340 cm⁻¹ are in coincidence with those of sodium salts of the aminoacids, respectively, which indicates that N—H group of the amino acid is not coordinated to the nickel atom⁸. No band was observed in the region 3 400—3 600 cm⁻¹ indicating the absence of free hydroxyl group of the amino acids in the above complexes. A strong band due to O—H deformation vibration appearing at ~935cm⁻¹ in the spectra of free carboxylic acids, was also absent in the spectra of the above derivatives indicating the attachment of carboxylic group with the nickel(II) through deprotonation¹². The absence of the characteristic carbonyl stretching frequency (found in the range 1 700—50 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of free carboxylic and amino acids) indicates the coordination of the carboxylate group to nickel(II) in these complexes¹³.

TABLE 2—MIXED CARBOXYLATO COMPLEXES OF Ni⁺⁺ (Ni(AA) (OOCR))

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Colour	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. wt.** Found/(Calcd.)
			Ni	N	AcOH (in azeotrope) g	
1.	Ni(leu)(myrist)	Green	14.07 (14.01)	3.30 (3.36)	0.29 (0.30)	1 260 (416)
2.	Ni(hip)(myrist)	Green	12.61 (12.65)	3.00 (3.02)	0.31 (0.32)	1 400 (484)
3.	Ni(leu)(palm)	Green	13.17 (13.22)	3.10 (3.15)	0.24 (0.25)	1 350 (444)
4.	Ni(hip)(palm)	Green	11.78 (11.93)	2.82 (2.85)	0.15 (0.16)	1 490 (492)
5.	Ni(leu)(ste)	Green	12.35 (12.43)	2.92 (2.97)	0.24 (0.25)	1 510 (472)
6.	Ni(hip)(ste)	Green	11.21 (11.29)	2.63 (2.69)	0.25 (0.26)	1 550 (520)

*palm = palmitic, ste = stearic, myrist = myristic acid anions ; all are solid.

**Ebullioscopically in benzene.

Results and Discussion

The methanol molecules in the complexes Ni(AA)₂.2MeOH could be removed at 140°/2 mm to give Ni(AA)₂ complexes, soluble in alcohol and 1,4-dioxan, and insoluble in benzene, toluene and chloroform. All the addition complexes, Ni(AA)₂.xL, where L = n-hexylamine (HexⁿNH₂), piperidine (pd), pyridine (py), 2,2'-bipyridine (2,2'-bipy), ethanol (EtOH), isopropanol (PrⁱOH), tertiarybutanol (Bu^tOH) and tetrahydrofuran (THF), were non-volatile and coloured solids, stable upto 80° (2 mm). The first and the second molecule of the added THF in the Ni(hip)₂.2THF complex, were found to be lost at 100° and 150° (2 mm), respectively.

In the present cases, the antisymmetric and symmetric C—O stretching frequencies have been observed at 1 530—1 640 and 1 430—1 470 cm⁻¹, respectively. The differences in these two frequencies are found lower than those of the corresponding alkali metal salts (195—210 cm⁻¹)¹⁴. Their positions and the differences clearly suggest the bidentate as well as bridging coordination of both the oxygen atom of the carboxylate group in all the above complexes^{15,16}. The shift to higher energies, i.e., 1 630—45 cm⁻¹ from 1 602 cm⁻¹ (for keto group) for the N-benzoylglycine excludes the possibility of this group to interact with the metal ions⁸. The coordinating nature of alcohol molecules in the alcohol-adducts is indicated by the presence of the

O—H stretching frequency towards the lower side (~ 3 100 cm^{-1}) compared to the free alcohols. In the adducts with tetrahydrofuran, a lowering in the C—O—C vibrations from 1 075 to 1 020 cm^{-1} indicate the coordinating behaviour of THF towards nickel atom.

The formation of coordinate bonds in bis(aminoacidato)nickel(II) adducts of the above nitrogen

of inter-electronic repulsion parameters are found below the free ion value (1 041 cm^{-1}) showing considerable covalent nature of the metal—ligand bond in all these nickel(II) complexes¹⁸. The ν_3/ν_1 ratio is found to be in the range 1.5—1.7, lowering of this value from 1.8 suggests high-spin octahedral complexes¹⁹. The values of covalency factor (β) ranges from 0.71 to 0.84 (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC* AND ESR SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF BIS-(AMINOACIDATO) AND MIXED CARBOXYLATO COMPLEXES OF Ni²⁺

Sl. no.	Compd.	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (ν_1)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (ν_2)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P) (ν_3)	B	C	β	ν_3/ν_1	g	μ_{eff}
1.	Ni(ieu) ₂	9 175	14 170	24 270	764	3 600	0.73	1.60	2.26	2.88
2.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2EtOH	9 250	14 925	24 580	784	3 695	0.75	1.61	2.19	2.94
3.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2Pr ^t OH	9 460	15 110	25 260	799	3 765	0.77	1.60	2.21	3.05
4.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2Bu ^t OH	9 670	14 540	25 630	744	3 505	0.71	1.50	2.23	2.96
5.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2THF	9 780	15 040	25 540	749	3 530	0.72	1.54	2.20	2.89
6.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2Hex ⁿ NH ₂	9 680	14 980	25 750	779	3 670	0.75	1.55	2.26	3.15
7.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2py	9 810	15 110	25 980	782	3 685	0.75	1.55	2.22	3.20
8.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2pd	9 640	15 050	25 480	774	3 645	0.74	1.56	2.19	2.98
9.	Ni(ieu) ₂ .2,2'-bipy	9 400	14 810	25 710	821	3 865	0.79	1.58	—	2.88
10.	Ni(hip) ₂	9 500	14 610	25 710	788	3 710	0.76	1.54	2.22	2.85
11.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2EtOH	9 720	14 815	26 100	784	3 695	0.75	1.52	2.23	2.97
12.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2Pr ^t OH	9 800	14 880	26 230	780	3 675	0.75	1.52	2.21	2.90
13.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2Bu ^t OH	9 840	15 015	26 460	797	3 755	0.77	1.53	2.25	2.92
14.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2THF	9 680	15 110	25 900	798	3 760	0.77	1.56	2.24	2.98
15.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2Hex ⁿ NH ₂	9 970	14 925	26 210	748	3 525	0.72	1.50	2.19	3.12
16.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2py	9 730	14 730	25 710	756	3 560	0.73	1.52	2.24	3.15
17.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2pd	9 770	15 090	25 620	760	3 580	0.73	1.54	2.22	3.21
18.	Ni(hip) ₂ .2,2'-bipy	9 825	15 210	26 140	792	3 730	0.76	1.55	2.14	3.18
19.	Ni(hip)(myrist)	8 620	15 040	23 890	871	4 100	0.84	1.74	2.16	3.19
20.	Ni(ieu)(myrist)	9 210	14 900	24 670	796	3 750	0.76	1.62	2.18	3.13
21.	Ni(hip)(palm)	8 770	15 240	24 050	865	4 075	0.83	1.74	2.17	3.16
22.	Ni(ieu)(palm)	9 260	14 910	24 470	773	3 640	0.74	1.61	2.20	3.18
23.	Ni(hip)(ste)	9 260	15 240	25 670	874	4 145	0.84	1.65	—	3.20
24.	Ni(ieu)(ste)	9 175	14 810	24 415	780	3 675	0.75	1.61	2.19	3.17

*Transitions, B and C are in cm^{-1} .

donor ligands is apparent from the considerable lowering (30—40 cm^{-1}) of N—H frequencies with respect to the free ligands¹⁵. The characteristic vibrations of pyridine ring at 706, 995 and 1 035 cm^{-1} are observed at 690, 1 015 and 1 050 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of the pyridine adducts, showing the considerable coordinating nature of the py ligand towards nickel(II) ion¹⁵. The splitting of ir band at 756 cm^{-1} (in free 2,2'-bipyridyl) to 768 and 750 cm^{-1} clearly indicates the coordinating behaviour of the ligand in these adducts¹⁵. The vibrations observed below 600 cm^{-1} may be ascribed due to Ni—N and Ni—O stretch¹⁵.

Electronic spectra: The spectra of the complexes are typical of divalent nickel in an octahedral environment, which exhibits three spin-allowed bands, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P), observed at 8 500—10 000 (ν_1), 14 500—15 500 (ν_2) and 23 000—26 000 cm^{-1} (ν_3), respectively. The transitions with their assignments and various other parameters are summarised in Table 3. The parameter B has been calculated by the equation given by Underhill and Billing¹⁷ $B = (\nu_3 + \nu_2 - 30 Dq)/15$. For a d⁸ system in an octahedral field, the lowest energy transition (ν_1) ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g} represents the 10 Dq. The values

Esr spectra and magnetic measurements: In an octahedral field, the ground state of nickel(II) is ³A_{2g} and the spin-orbit coupling does not split into the $m_s = 0$ and ± 1 level and thus an esr spectrum is not fully observed. But for the present complexes, one signal was observed in the esr spectra in polycrystalline state, enabling a precise evaluation of g values calculated by the method of Kneubuhl²⁰ and presented in Table 3. The experimental g values (2.13—2.27) were found to be higher than that for free-electron value (2.002 3) which was quite expected in view of the higher (than S.O.) magnetic moment due to the negative value of the spin-orbit coupling constant of the d⁸ system.

The magnetic moment values (μ_{eff} , 2.85—3.20 B.M.) of the complexes (Table 3) correspond to typical nickel(II) in the high-spin octahedral environment²¹. The magnetic moment values are higher than the spin-only value of 2.83 B.M. for two unpaired electrons which is typical for d⁸ system due to spin-orbit coupling^{21, 22}.

Molecular weights and plausible structures: Molecular weights (Tables 1 and 2) of the nickel(II) complexes determined either ebullioscopically or cryoscopically show that the Ni(AA)(OOCR)

complexes are trimeric²³ in refluxing benzene, while the Ni(AA)₂ and Ni(AA)₂.xL dimeric.

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